

Creating prescription maps from satellite imagery for site-specific management of cotton root rot

Chenghai Yang^{*1}, Xiaoyu Song², Mingqun Wu³, Robert L. Nichols⁴

¹ U.S. Department of Agriculture, Agricultural Research Service, Aerial Application Technology Research Unit, 3103 F & B Road, College Station, Texas 77845, USA

² Beijing Research Center for Information Technology in Agriculture, Beijing Academy of Agriculture and Forestry Sciences, Beijing 100097, China

³ The State Key Laboratory of Remote Sensing Science, Institute of Remote Sensing and Digital Earth, Chinese Academy of Sciences, P.O. Box 9718, Datun Road, Chaoyang, Beijing 100101, China

⁴ Cotton Incorporated, 6399 Weston Parkway, Cary, North Carolina 27513, USA

Abstract

Cotton root rot is a century-old cotton disease that can now be controlled with Topguard Terra Fungicide. However, as this disease tends to occur in the same general areas within fields year after year, site-specific treatment can be more effective and economical. The objective of this study was to evaluate GeoEye-1 and Sentinel-2 satellite multispectral imagery for creating prescription maps for site-specific management of this disease. A GeoEye-1 2-m image acquired in 2009 and a Sentinel-2A 10-m image acquired in 2016 were used to map cotton root rot in two cotton fields, respectively. The multispectral images were classified into root rot-infested and non-infested areas using unsupervised classification. To accommodate the potential expansion and temporal variation of the disease, a 10-m buffer around the infested areas was added as part of the treatment areas in the prescription maps. The prescription map from the GeoEye-1 image for Field 1 was used for site-specific fungicide application in 2016 and the disease was effectively controlled. Airborne 1-m multispectral imagery acquired in 2016 was used to validate the classification accuracy of the Sentinel-2A image for mapping the disease in Field 2. Although the Sentinel-2A image missed some small infested areas as compared with the airborne imagery, prescription maps with the 10-m buffer from the Sentinel-2A and airborne images were very similar. The results from this study indicate that historical satellite images with 10-m spatial resolution or finer can be used to create prescription maps for site-specific management of cotton root rot.

Background

Cotton root rot, caused by the soilborne fungus *Phymatotrichopsis omnivora*, is a destructive cotton disease occurring throughout the southwestern United States and northern Mexico (Percy, 1983). The symptoms usually begin during extensive vegetative growth, are more visible during flowering and fruit development, and continue through the growing season (Smith et al., 1962). The fungus kills plants typically in circular areas ranging from less than a square meter to several hectares in size. It is not unusual for over half of the plants in a cotton field to be killed by the disease in certain areas (Smith et al., 1962). Plants infected earlier in the growing season will die before bearing fruit, whereas infection occurring at later growth stages will reduce cotton yield and lower lint quality (Ezekiel and Taubenhaus, 1934; Yang et al., 2005).

Effective practices for the control of this century-old disease were lacking until Topguard® Fungicide was found to suppress this disease in field studies (Isakeit et al., 2009, 2012). Topguard is a commercial formulation of flutriafol from Cheminova, Inc. (Wayne, New Jersey) that is now part of FMC Corporation (Philadelphia, Pennsylvania). It was used effectively in Texas from 2012 to 2015 to control cotton root rot under Section 18 emergency exemptions granted by the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (EPA). As a result, growers achieved lower cotton root rot incidence, higher yields, and better fiber quality (Drake et al., 2013). In early 2015, Topguard® Terra Fungicide, a new, more concentrated formulation of flutriafol developed specifically for this market, was registered by the EPA.

Remote sensing studies have demonstrated that cotton root rot tends to occur in the same general areas within fields year after year, even though weather and cultural practices may affect its initiation and severity (Yang et al., 2016). The unique spatial nature of cotton root rot and its reoccurrence in the same areas across years make it an excellent candidate for site-specific management.

Therefore, it is necessary to define the infested areas within the field so that variable rate technology can be used to apply the fungicide only to the infested areas for more effective and economical control.

Airborne imagery has been successfully used to map the extent of cotton root rot infestations near the end of the growing season when cotton root rot is fully pronounced for the season (Yang et al., 2005) and to monitor the progression of the infections within cotton fields during a growing season (Yang et al., 2014). Although airborne imagery is available for cotton growing areas, it may have not been taken toward the end of the growing seasons. Therefore, high resolution satellite imagery can be a useful image source because of its high revisit frequency and relatively large geographic coverage. Recent developments in high resolution satellite sensors have significantly narrowed the gap in spatial resolution between traditional satellite imagery and airborne imagery. Since the first high resolution satellite sensor IKONOS was launched in 1999, numerous commercial high resolution satellite sensors have become available. Most of these satellites offer multispectral imagery with resolutions less than 5 m, including GeoEye-1, WorldView-3 and WorldView-4. Other sensors offer multispectral imagery with spatial resolutions from 5 to 10 m, including RapidEye, Sentinel-2A and Sentinel-2B. The objective of this study was to evaluate GeoEye-1 2-m and Sentinel-2A 10-m satellite multispectral imagery for creating prescription maps for site-specific management of cotton root rot.

Methods

A GeoEye-1 satellite image acquired by DigitalGlobe, Inc. (Longmont, Colorado) on July 27, 2009 and a Sentinel-1A satellite image acquired by the European Space Agency (Paris, France) on July 20, 2016 were used to map cotton root rot in two cotton fields, respectively, for this study. The GeoEye-1 image covered a 93-ha irrigated cotton field near Edroy, Texas with the field center coordinates (28°01'28"N, 97°44'53"W), referred to as Field 1. The Sentinel-2A image covered an 82-ha dryland cotton field in the nearby area with the field center coordinates (28°01'11"N, 97°40'37"W), referred to as Field 2. Both fields had a history of cotton root rot. The GeoEye-1 image contained four spectral bands in blue (450-510 nm), green (510-580 nm), red (655-690), and near-infrared (NIR, 780-920 nm) with a spatial resolution of 2 m and a dynamic range of 11 bits. The Sentinel-2A image contained 13 spectral bands with varying spatial resolutions of 10, 20 or 60 m, but only the four visible to NIR bands (i.e., blue, green, red and NIR) with a spatial resolution of 10 m were used.

An airborne two-camera imaging system was used to take images to monitor the performance of the site-specific treatment for Field 1 and for comparison with the Sentinel-2A image for Field 2 during the 2016 growing season. The two-camera system consisted of two Nikon D810 digital cameras with a 7360 x 4912 pixel array. One camera captured red-green-blue (RGB) color images, while the other camera was equipped with an 830-nm long-pass filter to obtain NIR images. The airborne images were acquired at 3200 m above ground level (AGL) with a pixel size of 0.8 m. The RGB and NIR images were aligned and stacked as a six-band image as the NIR image contained three NIR bands. Since the three NIR bands were similar, the NIR image recorded in the red channel was used. The aligned or registered images were then rectified to the Universal Transverse Mercator (UTM), World Geodetic System 1984 (WGS-84), Zone 14, coordinate system based on a set of ground control points around each field located with a Trimble GPS Pathfinder ProXRT receiver (Trimble Navigation Limited, Sunnyvale, California). All procedures for image registration and rectification were performed using ERDAS Imagine (Intergraph Corporation, Madison, Alabama). The GeoEye-1 and Sentinel-2A satellite images were rectified to the same coordinate system at delivery.

The prescription maps were created from the GeoEye-1 image for Field 1 and from the Sentinel-2A image for Field 2. A field boundary or an area of interest (AOI) was defined for each field and a normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) image was created within the AOI for each field. The NDVI images were then classified into root rot-infested and non-infested zones using ISODATA (Iterative Self-Organizing Data Analysis) unsupervised classification (Intergraph Corporation, 2013). To accommodate the potential expansion and temporal variation of the disease, a 10-m buffer around the infested areas were added as part of the treatment areas in the prescription maps.

Results and discussion

Figures 1 and 2 show the color-infrared (CIR) images, corresponding two-zone classification maps, and two-zone prescription maps for Fields 1 and 2, respectively. On the CIR images, root rot-infested plants had a brownish to greenish color, while the non-infested plants had a reddish tone. The root rot-infested areas can be easily distinguished from the non-infested areas on the CIR images. A visual comparison of the unsupervised classification maps with the CIR images reveals that the two-zone classification maps effectively identified root rot-infested areas within the fields. The 10-m buffers added to the infested areas in the classification maps effectively eliminated the non-infested small areas around the infested areas, making the prescription maps more practical for site-specific application.

Figure 1. (a) A GeoEye-1 color-infrared image, (b) a corresponding two-zone classification map and (c) a prescription map for a 93-ha irrigated cotton field near Edroy, Texas (Field 1).

Figure 2. (a) A Sentinel-2A color-infrared image, (b) a corresponding two-zone classification map and (c) a prescription map for an 82-ha dryland cotton field near Edroy, Texas (Field 2).

Table 1 presents in hectares and percentage the root rot-infested area from the classification maps and the prescribed treatment area with the 10-m buffer in the prescription maps for Fields 1 and 2. Only 3.2% of Field 1 was infested as determined from the classification map. With a 10-m buffer added to the infested areas, 7.9% of the field was prescribed as treatment area. About 23% of Field 2 was infested, while 33.5% of the field was prescribed as treatment area with a 10-m buffer. Clearly, the addition of the buffer zones significantly increased the treatment area for each field. The selection of the optimal buffer distance depends on factors such as infestation pattern, image availability of a single season or multiple seasons, planting swath, and the producer's risk tolerance.

Table 1. Root rot-infested area from classification maps and treatment area with a 10-m buffer in prescription maps for Fields 1 and 2.

Field	Satellite image	Imaging year	Field area (ha)	Classification area		Prescription area	
				(ha)	(%)	(ha)	(%)
1	GeoEye-1	2009	93.0	3.0	3.2	7.4	7.9
2	Sentinel-2A	2016	81.6	19.0	23.3	27.4	33.5

The prescription map created from the GeoEye-1 image for Field 1 was used for site-specific fungicide application at planting in 2016. Airborne multispectral images taken during the growing season showed that the fungicide effectively controlled the disease in the treated areas. Airborne multispectral imagery acquired in 2016 for Field 2 was used to evaluate the classification accuracy of the Sentinel-2A image for mapping the disease. The percent infested area estimated from the airborne image taken on July 11, 2016 was 21.5% compared with 23.3% based on the Sentinel-2A image. With a 10-m buffer, the percent treatment area from the airborne image was 36.9% compared with 33.5% based on the Sentinel-2A image. Although the Sentinel-2A image missed some small infested areas as shown on the airborne imagery, the prescription maps with the 10-m buffer from the Sentinel-2A and airborne images were very similar.

Conclusion

The results from this study indicate that historical satellite images with spatial resolutions of 10 m or finer can be used to create prescription maps for site-specific management of cotton root rot. Airborne and satellite imagery with spatial resolutions of 2 m or finer can accurately identify root rot infestations with small areas, but satellite imagery with 10-m spatial resolution is sufficient to map root rot with relatively large infestations. Most of the high resolution satellite sensors offer imagery with spatial resolutions of

5 m or finer. Some satellite sensors such as Sentinel-2A and -2B offer 10-m imagery for free. Unsupervised classification applied to original multispectral imagery or the NDVI imagery appears to be effective for creating root rot classification maps. Buffer zones should be added around the infested areas in the classification maps for generating prescription maps. The methods and results presented in this paper provide general guidelines for the creation of prescription maps and have practical implications for site-specific management of cotton root rot.

Acknowledgments

This project was partly funded by Cotton Incorporated, Cary, North Carolina. The authors wish to thank Lee Denham and Fred Gomez of USDA-ARS in College Station, Texas for taking the airborne imagery for this study. Thanks are also extended to Matt Setliff of Corpus Christi, Texas for allowing us to use his field. Mention of trade names or commercial products in this article is solely for the purpose of providing specific information and does not imply recommendation or endorsement by the U.S. Department of Agriculture. USDA is an equal opportunity provider and employer.

References

- Drake DR, Minzenmayer RR, Multer WL, Isakeit T, Morgan GD 2013. Evaluation of farmer applications of Topguard (flutriafol) for cotton root rot control in the first Section 18 exemption year. Proceedings of Beltwide Cotton Conferences, National Cotton Council of America, Memphis, Tennessee. Pp.152–156.
- Ezekiel WN, Taubenhaus JJ 1934. Cotton crop losses from *Phymatotrichum* root rot. *Journal of Agricultural Research* 49(9): 843–858.
- Intergraph Corporation (2013). ERDAS Field Guide. Intergraph Corporation, Huntsville, Alabama.
- Isakeit T, Minzenmayer RR, Sansone CG 2009. Flutriafol control of cotton root rot caused by *Phymatotrichopsis omnivora*. Proceedings of Beltwide Cotton Conferences, National Cotton Council of America, Memphis, Tennessee. Pp.130–133.
- Isakeit T, Minzenmayer RR, Drake DR, Morgan GD, Mott DA, Fromme DD, Multer WL, Jungman M, Abrameit A 2012. Fungicide management of cotton root rot (*Phymatotrichopsis omnivora*): 2011 results. Proceedings of Beltwide Cotton Conferences, National Cotton Council of America, Memphis, Tennessee. Pp.235–238.
- Percy RG 1983. Potential range of *Phymatotrichum omnivorum* as determined by edaphic factors. *Plant Disease* 67: 981–983.
- Smith HE, Elliot FC, Bird LS 1962. Root rot losses of cotton can be reduced. Pub. No. MP361. Texas A&M Agricultural Extension Service, College Station, Texas.
- Yang C, Fernandez CJ, Everitt JH 2005. Mapping *Phymatotrichum* root rot of cotton using airborne three-band digital imagery. *Transactions of the ASAE* 48(4): 1619–1626.
- Yang C, Odvody GN, Fernandez CJ, Landivar JA, Minzenmayer RR, Nichols RL, Thomasson JA 2014. Monitoring cotton root rot progression within a growing season using airborne multispectral imagery. *Journal of Cotton Science* 18(1): 85–93.
- Yang C, Odvody GN, Thomasson JA, Isakeit T, Nichols RL 2016. Change detection of cotton root rot infection over 10-year intervals using airborne multispectral imagery. *Computers and Electronics in Agriculture* 123: 154–162.